

KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE OF MOTHERS REGARDING ZINC SUPPLEMENTS IN DIARRHEAL PATIENTS UNDER FIVE YEARS OF AGE

Ayesha Rehman,¹ Namra Nazir,² Muhammad Naqash,³ Rizwan Gohar,⁴ Agha Shabbir Ali⁵

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Abstract

Background: Diarrhea is a global disease affecting people of all ages but causes high rate of mortality and morbidity in children of under 5 years of age especially in developing countries like Pakistan. According to world bank collection of development indicators, in Pakistan prevalence of diarrhea (percentage under 5 years of age) was 23.7%.

Objective: To determine knowledge, attitude and practice of mothers regarding zinc supplementation in diarrheal patients under 5 years of age.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study was conducted in pediatrics out-patient department of Lahore General Hospital Lahore from April 2019 to July 2019. We conducted a survey-based study on a group of 100 mothers to elicit information about knowledge, attitude and practice of mothers regarding zinc supplements in acute diarrhea in children under 5 years of age.

Results: A total 100 mothers were enrolled in the study. Of these, 9% belonged to rural area and 91% were from urban areas. 35% were uneducated and 65% educated. 82% were housewives while 18% were working ladies, out of which 9% belongs to health setup. 34% of mothers had the knowledge about zinc supplement and also practiced it while 66% had no knowledge regarding zinc and hadn't practiced zinc either.

Conclusion: By applying chi-square test, results showed that there was no significant relationship between education of mothers and the knowledge, attitude and practice of zinc supplementation. In addition to domestic techniques and ORS use, Zinc is one of the major components used for the treatment of diarrheal diseases under 5 years of children but the use of zinc by the mothers is quite low. To make the use of zinc effective and beneficial for children, awareness programs and advertisements can play a major role. These programs can make mothers well aware about the correct use of zinc supplements for the treatment of diarrhea.

Key Words: Zinc, supplement, diarrhea

Diarrhea is one of the most common causes of morbidity and mortality in children under 5 years of age.¹ As stated by WHO and UNICEF, every year 2 billion cases of diarrheal diseases are reported

and 1.9 million children of under 5 years lose their lives due to diarrhea, in developing countries. It can be estimated that on an average >5000 deaths occur each day due to diarrheal infection as after pneumonia, diarrhea is the 2nd leading cause of death worldwide.² In under developed countries, every child below 5 years experiences 2-9 episodes of diarrhea each year.³ From last few decades, due to betterments in the ORS techniques and reforms in sanitary and hygienic measures, the death rate due to diarrhea has decreased tremendously from 5 million annually to 1.5 million deaths in 2004 but diarrhea still prevails at the same rate.⁴

1. Ayesha Rehman
 2. Namra Nazir
 3. Muhammad Naqash
 4. Rizwan Gohar
 5. Agha Shabbir Ali
- 1-3. Ameer-ud-Din Medical College, Lahore
4,5. Pediatrics Department, Lahore General Hospital

Correspondence:

Dr. Rizwan Gohar, Assistant Professor Pediatrics, LGH, Ameer-ud-Din Medical College, Lahore

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That's why improvements are still needed for declining this high rate of incidence of diarrhea.

Oral rehydration salts play an important role in the treatment of dehydrating diarrhea, resulting in reduced mortality but don't decrease the duration of episodes or their consequences, such as malnutrition. From the last few years, along with ORS zinc has become a necessary adjunct for the treatment of diarrhea in children under 5 years of age. Zinc is an essential trace element and 2nd most abundant metal in humans after iron. It is required for the proper functioning of approx. more than 300 enzymes and 1000 transcription factors and cell growth.⁵ Zinc is necessary for better absorption of water and electrolytes by intestine.

It maintains healthy immune system of human body specially by removal of pathogens from the gut during diarrheal episode. According to the U.S. Institute of Medicine (IOM) updated Estimated Average Requirements (EARs) and Recommended Dietary Allowances (RDAs) for zinc for infants up to 12 months is 3 mg/day. For children ages 1–13 years the RDA increases with age from 3 to 8 mg/day. Zinc deficiency causes depressed growth, diarrhea, impotence and delayed sexual maturation, alopecia, eye and skin lesions, impaired appetite, altered cognition, impaired immune functions, defects in carbohydrate utilization, and reproductive teratogenesis. Zinc deficiency depresses immunity, but excessive zinc does also. Zinc deficiency is the important cause of diarrhea in children under 5 year of age with high mortality rate. Recent studies have shown that zinc when used along with low osmolarity ORS leads to decrease in frequency of acute persistent diarrhea.⁶ WHO and UNICEF recommend zinc with ORS in the dose of 20 mg daily for 10-14 days for children and 10 mg per day for infants below six months of age in the treatment for diarrhea⁷. In 2004, The WHO & UNICEF jointly recommended the use of low osmolarity ORS and Zinc supplementation for the control of diarrhea. But the coverage of ORT varies between 2-16% in India.⁸ In 2005 zinc has become part of essential drug list for the treatment of diarrhea

in the integrated management of childhood illness (IMNCI) and WHO.⁹

As mother is the prime caretaker of a child, so mother's knowledge plays an important role in the treatment of diarrheal episodes. Proper knowledge of treatment, awareness regarding use of zinc supplements and other techniques and practice of previous and new therapy for the diarrheal management are important steps taken by mother for the complete recovery from acute diarrhea. Lack of mother's knowledge and awareness about diarrheal management techniques leads to improper use of treatment strategies¹⁰. This study is based on the evaluation of knowledge, attitude and practices of mothers regarding zinc supplements in acute diarrhea in children under 5 years of age by assessing their educational level, occupation and source of information.

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted at pediatrics outpatient department, Lahore General Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan. Mothers of children under five years of age were identified and assessed about their knowledge regarding zinc supplementation in diarrheal infection. It was prospective cross-sectional study aimed to find out the awareness level of mothers about zinc for the treatment of diarrhea, which is a major childhood problem in the developing countries.

This study was carried out from 10th March 2019 – 1st June 2019. Total 100 mothers were engaged over this period and information was obtained. Ethical Approval was taken from the department.

The data was analyzed using statistical package SPSS windows version 25. A p value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. The student t-test was used to compare arithmetic means and parameters while Chi square(X²) test were used to compare categorical data. The bivariate regression analysis was done for different factors.

RESULTS

A total of 100 mothers were enrolled to assess the knowledge, attitude and practice of zinc supple-

ments in children under 5 years of age for treatment of diarrhea. The demographic details are given in table 1.

Out of 100 mothers only 34% had the knowledge about when to give zinc supplementation in case of diarrhea while other 66% do not have the

Table 1: Demographic Details

		Fre- quency	Per- cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Residence	Rural	9	9	9	9
	Urban	91	91	91	100
	Total	100	100	100	-
Education	Uneducated	35	35	35	35
	upto 5th grade	15	15	15	50
	upto 8th grade and above	24	24	24	74
	Graduated	26	26	26	100
	Total	100	100	100	-
Occup- ation	Housewife	82	82	82	82
	working woman	18	18	18	100
	Total	100	100	100	-

knowledge. Out of these 34, 9 belongs to health setup while other 25 do not belong to health setup.

Out of 100 mothers 20% had the good, 20% had satisfactory, 2% had poor perception about zinc supplementation while 66% don't know about zinc

supplementation. Out of 100 mothers, 32% told that treatment is effective while 2% told that treatment is not effective while 66% had no idea about the treatment.

Out of 100 mothers, 34% had given while 66% had not given zinc supplementation to their child.

Out of 34 mothers who had given Zinc Supplements, 18% had given by herself while 82% had given Zinc Supplements on Doctor's Opinion.

Out of 34 mothers who had given Zinc Supplements, 3% told that the effect appeared after 1 day, 56% told after 1-2 days, 26% told after 2-3 days, 15% told after 3 or more days.

Out of 34 mothers who had given Zinc Supplements to the children whenever they suffer from diarrhea, 53% had given zinc supplements after every diarrheal disease, 47% had not given after every diarrheal disease.

Out of 34 mothers who had given Zinc Supplements, 88% had noticed response, 12% had noticed no response.

On application of chi square test, the correlation of knowledge, attitude and practice about zinc therapy with education of mother was found to be non-

Correlation of Knowledge of Zinc Supplements with Education of Mother						
Do you know when to give Zinc Supplements?		Yes	No	Total		
Education	Uneducated	10	25	35		
	Upto 5th Grade	5	10	15		
	Upto 8th Grade & Above	8	16	24		
	Graduated	12	14	26		
	Total	35	65	100		
Correlation of attitude about zinc therapy with education of moth						
What is your perception about Zinc Treatment?		Good	Satisfactory	Poor	Don't Know	Total
Education	Uneducated	4	3	2	26	35
	Upto 5th Grade	1	4	0	10	15
	Upto 8th Grade & Above	5	3	0	16	24
	Graduated	10	2	0	14	26
	Total	20	12	2	66	100
Correlation of Practice of Zinc Supplements with Education of Mother						
Do you know when to give Zinc Supplements?		Yes	No	Total		
Education	Uneducated	7	28	35		
	Upto 5th Grade	1	14	15		
	Upto 8th Grade & Above	7	17	24		
	Graduated	9	17	26		
	Total	24	76	100		

significant. The p value was greater than 0.05.

DISCUSSION

Diarrhea is the major cause of morbidity and mortality in children. According to UNICEF and WHO, in developing countries 2 billion cases of diarrheal cases are reported every year and 1.9 million children of under 5 years died due to diarrhea. According to world bank collection of development indicators, in Pakistan prevalence of diarrhea (% under 5 years of age) was reported to be 23.7% in 2013. In this Study, our aim was to determine the knowledge, attitude and practices of mothers about reduction of Diarrhea by using Zinc Supplements. According to a research in India, only 1.9% mothers had heard of Zinc therapy. UNICEF reported that the knowledge about Zinc therapy in mothers was almost equal to zero.¹¹ Similarly, low levels of knowledge were reported by Rukkappanavar et al¹², where only 3.8% of mothers gave zinc. Recent studies have been done in Bangladesh and Kenya where rate of zinc awareness and administration was 35% and 32% respectively.¹³ According to our study, only 34% of mothers are well aware of zinc supplements and are practicing zinc for the treatment of Diarrhea. A study in India reported that Education levels and Occupation of the mother play significant role in knowledge about Zinc supplements. In contrary to this, in our study there was no association of education and occupation of mothers with awareness about zinc supplements. Even mothers belonging to health professional didn't have significant knowledge about zinc supplementation. Our study has revealed the low knowledge about zinc supplementation in Diarrhea. It emphasized on the need and pointed out the importance of Health education in familiarizing zinc supplementation among mothers because mother plays the most significant role in family care at home. The criteria of our study were hospital based which had a number of limitations. Better sources of information in this regard could be community based and multicentric studies. A case control study can be a better idea for knowing about

compliance of zinc therapy because in case control study we can do follow up of patients for a long time to know about merits and demerits of zinc supplementation in diarrheal patients.

CONCLUSION

By applying chi-square test, results showed that there was no significant relationship between education of mothers and the knowledge, attitude and practice of zinc supplementation. In addition to domestic techniques and ORS use, Zinc is one of the major components used for the treatment of diarrheal diseases under 5 years of children but the use of zinc by the mothers is quite low. To make the use of zinc effective and beneficial for children, awareness programs and advertisements can play a major role. These programs can make mothers well aware about the correct use of zinc supplements for the treatment of diarrhea.

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